

TO STUDY IMPACT OF NEP2020 ON RURAL PRIMARY EDUCATION

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Abstract

Socio-eco-political perceptions of education are changing. The change is directly proportional to the social classes including OBC/SC/ST/VJ NT/ DNT/SBC. The NEP2020 has many significant social, economical, lifelong values concern with Indian Rural Primary Education aren't proven scientifically.

NEP2020 ensures to do major reforms that bring the highest quality, equity, and integrity into the system from early childhood care, education, curriculum, and pedagogy in school, teachers capacity building re-establish them at all levels of the most respected and essential members of our society. It bonds with legacies to the world heritage, nurture, preservation, and posterity of Indian culture and philosophy, dominates upper-class monarchy. It promotes lifelong opportunities for all regardless of social and economical background. Access to privatization prefers to sabotage the representation of backward, constitutional stakeholders. Enforcement through the private sector simultaneously declines the ratio of representation through NEP2020 is ensuring all students are provided various targeted opportunities to enter and Excel in the educational system.

NEP2020 is promoting school complex accreditation for school education. It is the consequence of closing all kinds of rural primary institutions.

Expertise cited their different aspects of NEP2020. The researcher has chosen this subject to inculcate inverse and direct influence on backward. Observations and survey methods enhance the credibility and reliability of collected data. Findings determine the adequate representation of SC/ST/OBC/VJ NT/DNT/SBC in worldwide opportunities of social-economical educational, cultural development.

It proves Rural Primary Education is under incline and decline influence of NEP2020.

Keywords: NEP-2020, Rural Primary Education, Discrimination, Privatisation, Constitution.

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Introduction:

In India, public expenditure on education as a percentage of GDP is 4.13. About 19,717 students are enrolled in primary and upper primary education. 25.4 males and 23.5 females are beneficiaries of primary education. The constitutional amendment that has made elementary education, a fundamental right, for every child ensuring the health, nutrition, and inclusive school environment empowering all children in there across differences of caste, religion, gender, disability (NCF-2005)

NCF-2005: It is seeking guidance from the constitutional vision of India as a secular, egalitarian, pluralistic society founded on the value of social justice and equality. Connecting Early Childhood Care and Education (ECCE) to primary school syllabi.[1]

What Is Primary Education?

Level in which 6 to 14 age group children enroll and get experiences with the help of a variety of tools in the presence of efficient teachers.

PRIMARY EDUCATION AS 2015-16 [3]:

Comprehensive Merit Management in Education: Management of comprehensive merit development is the strategic part of planning for the management of enforcement. It includes 1. Detailed Description 2. Limitation of Time and Period 3. Distribution of Resources 4. Observation of result-oriented indicators.[2]

Level	ALL			SC			ST		
	Male	Female	Total	Male	Female	Total	Male	Female	Total
Primary (I-V)	97.9	100.7	99.2	109.5	112.4	110.9	107.8	105.7	106.7
Upper Primary (VI-VIII)	88.7	97.6	92.8	97.8	107.7	102.4	95.4	98.2	96.7
Elementary (I-VIII)	94.5	99.6	96.9	105.3	110.8	107.9	103.4	103.1	103.3

REASONS FOR DROPOUT:

Sl. No.	Major reasons for drop-out	Percentage	
		Male	Female
1	Child not interested in studies	23.80%	15.60%
2	Financial Constraints	23.70%	15.20%
3	Engage in Domestic Activities	4.80%	29.70%
4	Engage in Economic Activities	31.00%	4.90%
5	School is far off	0.5%	3.40%
6	Unable to cop-up with studies	5.4%	4.60%
7	Completed desired level/ Class	5.70%	6.50%
8	Marriage		13.90%
9	Other reasons*	5.1%	6.20%

DISTANCE FROM SCHOOL HAVING PRIMARY AND UPPER PRIMARY LEVEL CLASSES:

Distance	Level	Rural	Urban	Combined
d<1km	Primary	941	925	936
	Upper Primary	665	829	718
	Secondary	367	727	484
1km≤d<2km	Primary	49	65	55
	Upper Primary	190	131	171
	Secondary	236	187	220
2km≤d<5km	Primary	9	8	9
	Upper Primary	121	37	94
	Secondary	275	80	211
d≥5km	Primary	1	1	1
	Upper Primary	24	2	17
	Secondary	122	7	85

ANALYTICAL SCENARIO OF NEP-2020 REFLECTED ON RURAL PRIMARY EDUCATION:

- What is NEP-2020?
 - A] This is only a document that is the government has published as NEP-2020
 - B] It is divided into four parts, School education, Higher education, Other key areas of focus, and Making it happen
 - C] Primary education is one of the levelsof education
 - D] Government said three objectives:
 1. Short-term objective – To publish NEP-2020 and To get mass influence.
 2. Middle-term objective – To do the enforcement of NEP-2020 with determining outcomes
 3. Long-term objective –
 - To establish determined agenda.
 - To promote privatisation.
 - To nullify representation of SC/ST/OBC/VJ/NT/DNT/MINORITY.
 - To deny scholarship and other educational schemes.
- Impact on –
 - Learner - Under the scheme of the school complex small schools should be merged in the school complex.

- KG To PG in the grip of Capitalist Bourgeois:

Conclusion:

Stay on Teacher's recruitment neglecting modification of schools proved policy and implications has contradictions. ECCE is showcasing art, music, physical education available on learner's economical ability. Economic Growth, Social Justice, Equality, Scientific Advancement, National Integration, and Cultural Preservation these values of Constitution will be going to vanish.

References:¹

- ¹1. Government of India , "NCF-2005"
2. Murrur Mukhopadhyay, "Comprehensive Merit Management"
3. Government of India, "Education on Statistic at a glance- 2018"